

Review Article

Mapping the Landscape of Artificial Intelligence Applications in Human Resources Management: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

The attractiveness of artificial intelligence (AI) in various commercial sectors has prompted to investigate the current state of AI in the field of human resource management (AIHRM). Scopus data from 2015 to 2023 was used to conduct a bibliometric analysis of AI-HRM, and the VOS viewer software programme was used for the analysis. The results indicate there was a notable rise in the quantity of publications starting in 2021, indicating that the field of "Artificial Intelligence" exhibits a stronger association with "Human Resource Management". Distinguish the publication seven clusters, i.e., Concept, ethic, and perception, interaction, literature, recruitment, and merge and application of AI with HRM. Further researchers may solicit to undertake a comprehensive investigation in the field of Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management (AIHRM) by integrating varied repositories of data. The findings highlight the increasing importance of artificial intelligence (AI) within the field of Human Resource Management (HRM), hence emphasizing the necessity for more investigation and incorporation of various data sources.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, author, bibliometric, human resource management.

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Introduction

In the realm of modern times, a vast majority of organizations across various sectors are actively integrating or contemplating the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into their operations (Füller, Hutter, Wahl, Bilgram, & Tekic, 2022). Industries such as telecommunications, engineering, financial services, customer service, healthcare, pharmaceuticals, and education institutions stand out as the foremost adopters of AI technologies (Perifanis & Kitsios, 2023). The exponential growth in digitization and the concurrent adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) have been significantly transforming the business environment (Javaid, Haleem, Singh, Suman, & Gonzalez, 2022). Artificial Intelligence has greatly influenced the way organizations operate, to the extent that it has become an essential aspect of corporate strategy (Kraus, Durst, Ferreira, Veiga, Kailer, & Weinmann, 2022). The Human Resources Management department was not distant in this particular transition. The role of human resource management (HRM) has experienced numerous evolutions, resulting in a reconfiguration of its inherent impact on both the micro-organizational and macroeconomic domains (Varallyai & Hmoud, 2023). The aforementioned transformations have been observed to engender a notable shift in the Human Resource Management (HRM) function, wherein there is a discernible increase in the emphasis placed on strategic considerations (Zhang & Chen, 2023). The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) within the realm of Human Resource Management (HRM) yields numerous benefits, including increased capacity, a broader range of perspectives, and enhanced analytical assistance, all of which serve to improve the management of personnel (Kaur, AG, AG, & Gandolfi, 2023).

In the process of transitioning human resource management (HRM) towards artificial intelligence (AI), numerous experts have been redirected to conduct research in the domain of AI-HRM. Qiu & Zhao (2019) focused on the impact of AI on HRM and analyzing its opportunities and risks can illuminate AI and lead to more effective HRM practices, a more fundamental shift in HRM, and the achievement of its stated goals of fostering a more adaptive and innovative workforce. A study from India states that the area of Human Resource Management (HRM) in particular has begun to pay more and more attention to the rapidly developing science of artificial intelligence (AI) (Chatterjee, Chaudhuri, Vrontis, Thrassou, & Ghosh, 2021). AI in marketing studies with a research agenda focused on AI allows HR departments to automate tedious, time-consuming operations, boosting both productivity and efficiency (Mustak, Salminen, Plé, & Wirtz, 2021). A healthcare study explains that adopting AI in human resource management is not only about streamlining routine tasks; it's also about shifting our mental models and organizational priorities (Leone, Schiavone, Appio, & Chiao, 2021). The introduction of AI into the HR sector brings in a new era of opportunity and promises revolutionary cost reductions for HR experts (Wisetsri, C.Vijai, Chueinwittaya, & Jirayus, 2022). Verma & Bandi, (2019) define that employee happiness as something that might be increased by integrating AI into human resources processes like onboarding and benefit administration.

At the same time, a major bibliometric study on AI-HRM found that most of the research has focused on how it can be used to recruit and choose staff, as well as for other important tasks like training, development, or employee rotation (Palos-Sánchez, Baena-Luna, Badicuc, & Infante-Moro, 2022). The AIHRMI framework highlighted a similar

finding regarding the integration of AI in Human Resource Management. It was discovered that the primary focus of essential research in this field is on the integration of AI into the many facets of human resource management, including recruiting, selection, onboarding, performance analysis, training and learning, talent acquisition, management, and retention (Kaushal, Kaurav, Sivathanu, & Kaushik, 2023). A Bibliometric study based on Scopus indexed between 2015 and 2022 states that the majority of studies on the development of AI and HRM depend on the conventional literature review, which is insufficient for providing an in-depth review of the research domain (Mathushan, Gamage, & Wachissara, 2023). Out of 247 papers in the AI- HRM that were indexed by Scopus between 1993 and 2020, the vast majority dealt with issues of talent acquisition, resource allocation, and training and development. Indicate the need for more study, particularly in the areas of systematic theory building, conceptual studies, and empirical investigations (Kaur, AG, AG, & Gandolfi, 2023).

In this particular context, the researcher is greatly inclined towards conducting a bibliometric analysis, drawing inspiration from the most up-to-date and relevant data that is currently accessible. These backgrounds develop the following question to study:

- What are the emerging patterns of publication growth in the field of AIHRM?
- Which are the most cited authors, publications and countries in the field of AIHRM?
- What are the literature streams, maps and temporal evolution?

Researchers and professionals in the field will benefit significantly from this study since it can assist them keep track of growing trends in AIHRM research papers, pinpointing influential authors, publications, and nations, and charting the evolution of literature streams over time.

Methodology

Bibliometrics is the study of patterns in the distribution of academic works on a certain topic using quantitative techniques (L, George, & P.S, 2023). Bibliometric examination has become increasingly significant due to its ability to provide comprehensive insights into a specific subject matter (Donthu, Kumar, & Mukherjee, 2021). Bibliometric analyses inform the reader on historical developments in the field, shed light on recent contributions to the field, and suggest avenues for future study (Hashem, Salleh, Abdullah, Ali, Faisal, & Nor, 2023). This study was basically based on Bibliometric analysis. Bibliometric analysis is essential for literature reviews to evaluate the significance and impact of published works quantitatively. The major reason to use bibliometric analysis is to allow researchers to identify trends, patterns, and collaborations in a specific field, providing a comprehensive understanding of its evolution (Donthu & Gustafsson, 2020).

Selection of Database

On July 3, 2023, a sample of Scopus papers published between 2015 and 2023 was chosen as a sample. Scopus was selected because Scopus is a prominent curated abstract and citation database that offers an extensive handle of scientific conference proceedings, journals, and books on a global and regional scale, and it maintains a commitment to indexing only the most reliable and superior quality data, achieved through a meticulous content selection process and subsequent evaluation conducted by an independent Content Selection and Advisory Board (Baas, Schotten, Plume, Côté, & Karimi, 2019). At the moment, Scopus covers a wider range of the academic literature than CrossRef open DOI-to-DOI citations and the Web of Science (WoS) (Thelwall & Sud, 2022), this is the major reasons to select Scopus database for this study.

Search criteria

The study utilized a set of specific keywords, namely "Artificial Intelligence," "Human Resource Management," "AI Human Resource Management," "Human Resources Artificial Intelligence," "AI for HRM," and "HRMAI," to compile a complete list of relevant papers. In light of the limited research on bibliometric analysis of HRM in the field of AI, researchers aim to expand upon the existing literature by examining papers that address the same issue, utilizing the document's title, abstract, and keywords. The aforementioned terms were queried as "Article Title, Abstract, Keywords" in the search process. The researcher conducted a thorough examination of the subject matter, excluding any topics that were not directly relevant to the field of HRM. A total of 79 documents were retrieved from the Scopus data, as depicted in Figure 1.

Measurement

The various software tools, such as Microsoft Excel, VOSviewer, and wordsift, were used for the purposes of data analysis and data visualization. Microsoft Excel was used to extract frequency, percentage and to display the Histogram. The VOSviewer was utilized for the majority of the mapping studies conducted in this study (Eck & Waltman, 2010). VOSviewer is a software tool that visually depicts the network of nodes, specifically highlighting both the number and overall strength of connections, through the utilization of two standardized weights (Kirby, 2023). VOSviewers was used to discover authors' productivity, publication rank, country co-authorship, Bibliographic coupling, bibliographic coupling temporal analysis, keyword co-occurrence network and key co-occurrence network temporal analysis. The Wordsift was used to figure out keywords.

Database
Scopus
Keyword
"Artificial Intelligence," "Human Resource Management," "AI Human Resource Management," "Human Resources Artificial Intelligence," "AI for HRM," and "HRMAI,"
Criteria Selection
Timespan: 2015-2023 Criteria: Title, Abstract, Keyword

Language: English Document types: Article, conference Filtered Subject categories: Human Resource Management Collected: 79 publication
Tools
VOSviewers, Microsoft Excel, WordSift
Analysis
Bibliographic coupling; keyword co-occurrence; temporal analysis. Frequency, percentage, Histogram Keywords visualization
Result
Discussion and conclusion in Artificial Intelligence Human Resource Management Current Stage

Figure 1. Workflow of the Paper

Result

Types of Publication

Table 1. List of Published Literature

S.N	Publication	Frequency	Percentage
1	Article	48	60.75%
2	Conference paper	31	39.24%

Source: Scopus Database, 2015-2023

Table 1 displays the Scopus category of literature along with its frequency and proportion. The category of articles dominated the most, with 60.75%, and the category of conference papers came in second with 39.24%.

Publication per year

Figure 2. Publication per year

Figure 2 shows the year-by-year literature on the subject matter that was published between 2015 and 2023. The survey found that 2022, with 27 (34.1%) of the total, was the most productive year, followed by 2023, with 25 (31.6%) up to 7/4/2023, and 2021, with 13 (16.4%) of the literature published. Conferring to the study, there has been a rise in the publication of literary works starting in 2020 with number 12, and this trend is expected to continue. The above findings indicate that there haven't been that many studies conducted in HRM-AI, which highlights the fact that there should be more study conducted in this area.

Authors Rank

Table 2. Authors productivity base on Citation

	Authors	Citation	Publisher	literature
1	Vrontis et al., (2022)	121	Routledge	Journal
2	jia et al., (2018)	60	ICEB	Conference paper
3	pan et al., (2022)	38	Routledge	Journal
4	Malik et al., (2022)	37	John Wiley & Sons Inc	Journal
5	johnson et al., (2020)	37	Emerald Group Holdings Ltd.	Journal
6	votto et al., (2021)	36	Elsevier Ltd	Journal
7	pereira et al., (2023)	30	Elsevier Ltd	Journal
8	Bhardwaj et al., (2020)	29	IEEEI	Conference paper
9	arслан et al., (2020)	25	Emerald Group Holdings Ltd.	Journal
10	qamar et al., (2021)	23	Emerald Group Holdings Ltd.	Journal

Source: Scopus Database, 2015-2023

In a total of 76 authors based on article cited that was published in AI-HRM title, 47 authors meet the threshold for the analyzed in setting the minimum document of author 1 and the minimum number of citations is 1. The above table shows that the most prolific were. Researchers rated them by total article citations to better categorize and comprehend their significance.

The most-cited study was by (Vrontis, Christofi, Pereira, Tarba, Makrides, & Trichina, 2022), which was referenced in 121 articles. Human resource management, sophisticated technology, artificial intelligence, and robots are all topics they systematically explore. Recruiting, training, and job performance were singled out as key areas of focus in the research, as were high-priority HRM methods such as human-robot/AI cooperation, job replacement, learning opportunities, and decision-making. Similarly, conference Papers by (Jia, Guo, Li, Li, & Chen, 2018) were referenced in 60 articles. The authors demonstrated the basic framework of AIHRM. Findings propose six primary AI applications in HRM (decision support, assessment, human-machine interaction, training advisor, and reward system). Pan, froese, liu, hu & ye, (2022) show the moderating impact of transaction costs on firms' technical competency and technological complexity. The findings indicate that the dimensions of company size and industry exhibit negligible impact on the utilization of artificial intelligence. Subsequently, the study by (Malik,

Budhwar, Mohan, & R, (2022) focused on a brand-new theoretical framework outlining the characteristics and objectives of a digitalized, AI-assisted HR ecosystem. They observed efficiency in employee productivity through AI. A descriptive study conducted by (Johnson, Stone, & Lukaszewski, 2020) describes AI and e-HRM as having the potential to revolutionize hiring processes in the hotel and tourism sectors. Fostered, caution must be used to guarantee that the conclusions reached and the choices made are well-received by the workforce and provide better results for the organization as a whole. In the same pace as the 36 referenced articles (Votto, Valecha, Najafirad, & Rao, 2021) offers valuable insights into the specific areas of tactical Human Resource Management (HRM) and Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) that receive attention, identifies gaps in existing research, and provides guidance for future research objectives. Additionally, it examines the components of tactical HRIS (T-HRIS) that are highlighted in the literature and explores the various portrayals of each T-HRIS component. Moreover, (Pereira, Hadjielias, Christofi, & Vrontis, 2023), (Bhardwaj, Singh, & Kumar, 2020), (Arslan, Cooper, Khan, Golgeci, & Ali, 2020), (Qamar, Agrawal, Samad, & Jabbour, 2021) articles were referenced at 30, 29, 25 and 23 respectively.

Publication Rank

Table 3. Ranking of publications most cited

S.N	Source	Documents	Citations
1	international journal of human resource management	3	196
2	proceedings of the international conference on electronic business (iceb)	1	60
3	journal of tourism futures	1	37
4	international journal of information management data insights	1	36
5	proceedings of international conference on computation, automation and knowledge management, iccakm 2020	1	29
6	journal of enterprise information management	1	23
7	international journal of speech technology	1	20
8	information systems frontiers	1	18
9	management research review	1	16
10	international journal of manpower	2	28
11	human resource management review	6	80

Source: Scopus Database, 2015-2023

The number of citations a published work has received is frequently used to determine its quality and reliability (Edinsel, 2023). It has been argued in the scientific literature that the number of times a publication is cited is proportional to its significance (Aksnes, Langfeldt, & Wouters, 2019). The most cited publication was the International Journal of Human Resource Management, with 196 citations representing three documents. The second most cited publication was the Conference of ICEB, with one document receiving 60 citations. The third most cited publication was the Journal of Tourism Futures, with one document and 37 citations. The lowest-category publication among the ten most cited

publications was Human Resource Management Review, with three documents and 80 citations.

Country Rank

Table 4. Top ten Co-authorship countries rank by Citation

ID	Country	Citations	Total link strength	Rank
35	United Kingdom	251	20	1
10	France	192	11	2
13	India	171	7	3
6	Cyprus	151	3	4
5	China	104	6	5
36	United States	85	10	7
27	Russian Federation	16	4	8
7	Denmark	25	3	9
20	Netherlands	20	3	10

Source: Scopus Database, 2015-2023

In a total of 37 countries, 27 countries meet the threshold for the analyzed in terms of the minimum document of country 1 and the minimum number of citations of country 1. Here in the above list, United Kingdom documents with 251 citations stand first with 20 total link strength, followed by France with 192 citations and 11 total link strength, and similarly, the United States ranks third with 171 citations but only 7 total link strength. Ten ranks were stated by the Netherlands with 20 citations and 3 total link strength

Co-authorship (Countries)

Figure 3 shows the distribution of co-authorship by country. Among the twenty-seven nations analyzed, the United Kingdom and France have the greatest co-authorship network, as seen in the figure. Australia, India, the United Arab Emirates, and the United Kingdom all have close working relationships. Countries like Denmark, Finland, and Sweden have a close working connection, and there is a close network cluster that includes Cyprus, France, and Morocco. A similar close network was shared by China, Germany, and Pakistan. Italy, Poland, and the Russian Federation (purple) are some of the other authors in this group. The networks were shared between the United States and South Korea and between the United States and Malaysia, respectively.

Figure 3. Co-authorship (Countries)
Source: Created through VOS viewers

Bibliometric Maps

Figure 5 shows the results of the keyword co-occurrence network analysis. Figure 4 shows the results of the bibliographic reference coupling analysis. This analysis covered the 79 publications that were released between 2015 and 2023.

Bibliographic coupling

Figure 4: Bibliographic coupling
Source: Created through VOS viewers

Bibliometric coupling analysis was performed using VOS viewer software in order to gain a deeper understanding of the domain and its evolving themes (Saini, Lievens, &

Srivastava, 2022). The research shows that there are seven distinct clusters (yellow, sky blue, blue, green, purple, red and orange), as shown in Figure 4.

Cluster Analysis

Red cluster consist of 8 articles. Cluster focused on Systematic review on AI-HRM (Basu, Majumdar, Mukherjee, Munjal, & Palaksha, 2023), AI capacity framework for maximizing the benefits of AIHRM (Chowdhury, et al., 2023), an updated concept of personal AI acceptance (Giudice, Scuotto, Orlando, & Mustilli, 2023), Artificial Intelligence's Effect on Human Resources Crisis Management: A COVID19 Analytical Study (Khalifa, Baz, & Muttar, 2022), Understanding the Antecedents and Consequences of AI-Mediated Knowledge Sharing and Exchange of HRM Practices (Malik, Budhwar, Mohan, & R., 2023).

Green cluster consist of 6 articles. Cluster focused on introducing a stakeholder-based analysis of algorithmic HRM's opacity, transparency, and measures for reducing opacity (Langer & Königa, 2021), Review of the literature on AI in HRM, with a recommended multilevel research approach (Priksat, Islam, Patel, Malik, Budhwar, & Gupta, 2023), Stakeholder-Centered Solutions for Human Resource Management AI Designing Fair AI in HRM: Addressing the Conflicts Over Algorithmic Rating (Park, Ahn, Hosanagar, & Lee, 2022), Dignified AI Decision-Making; Analyzing the Differences between Human and AI Decision Making from an HRM Perspective (Bankins, Formosa, Griep, & Richards, 2022) and Ethical considerations for HR professionals when implementing AI technology (Bankins, 2021).

Blue cluster consist of 6 articles. Cluster focused on Team-level interactions between AI and humans in the workplace; a conceptual analysis of the difficulties and opportunities for human resource management (Arslan, Cooper, Khan, Golgeci, & Ali, 2020), The effects of AI on the job market for recent college grads in Germany and the Netherlands: a comparative analysis Possibilities and dangers of AI (Rauf, Ashfaq, Hasan, & Manju, 2021), Performance Expectation and Social Influence on Employees' and Management's Trust in AI (Figueroa-Armijos, Clark, & Veiga, 2002), HR departments that use AI to make better decisions (Hmoud, 2021).

Yellow cluster consist of 6 articles. Cluster focused on literature review and bibliometric analysis, into the intersection of AIHRM (Kaushal, Kaurav, Sivathanu, & Kaushik, 2023), similar review was conducted by (Tewari & Pant, 2020) on AI reshaping HRM. Another study in yellow cluster consists of Literature Review on the Application of AI to Tactical HRM (Votto, Valecha, Najafirad, & Rao, 2021). Studying AI's potential influence on the establishment of efficient project teams (Rajpurohit, Saxena, Yadav, & Chande, 2020) was also major study fall under this cluster. Basically, study falls under this cluster focus on the literature review of AI-HRM.

This cluster contain five publications, which focus on HR management and the rise of AI in the recruitment procedure (Ochmann & Laumer, 2020), Contextual variables' influence on the use of AI in recruitment (Pan, Froese, Liu, Hu, & Ye, 2022), examination of published works on the topic of using AI for hiring and staffing (Rezzani, Caputo, & Cortese, 2020). Among five three publications on AI in recruitment process of Human in

an organization remain two publications focused on the study in advanced technology in HRM by (Vrontis, Christofi, Pereira, Tarba, Makrides, & Trichina, 2022) and AI adoption and its impact by (Agarwal, 2023).

Light blue cluster cover four publication, among them three study raise the issue on when Humans and Machines Collide: The Power of Hybrid Intelligence to Drive Game-Changing Innovation through Extended Selves and Collaborative Skills by (Abbas, Liu, & Khushnood, 2022) , when technology meets people; AIHRM by (Qamar, Agrawal, Samad, & Jabbour, 2021) and Human Resource factorization in AI (Panicker, Sharma, & Khandelwa, 2022), Another publication focus on advantages of AI and eHRM for talent acquisition (Johnson, Stone, & Lukaszewski, 2020).

Orange cluster cover four publications on application and research of HRM through AI background (Wang & Lin, 2020), AI application in HRM practices by (Tiwari, Pandey, Garg, & Singhal, 2021) and remain two publications focus on AI and HR Functions: An Empirical Study (Bhardwaj, Singh, & Kumar, 2020) and multi-process literature assessment on AI's effects on workplace outcomes (Pereira, Hadjielias, Christofi, & Vrontis, 2023). From the analysis orange cluster mainly focused on the application of AI-HRM.

Keyword co-occurrence network

The basic VOS Viewer standard that rises keywords that appear at least 5 times in the sample leads to the presentation of 16 of the 586 keywords that were recognized as being potential candidates for presentation (see Figure 5). Results demonstrate that "Artificial Intelligence" was the most commonly encountered period of time, with 69 occurrences and 145 linkages to other keywords (see Figure 6), confirming that AI-HRM are the two core themes of this investigation. The term "Human Resource Management" also showed up 46 times, and there were 140 links to related articles. Several common umbrella phrases were also discovered in this analysis, including: resources allocation (21 occurrences, 94 links), Natural resources management (20 occurrences, 89 links), human resources management (23 occurrences, 88 links), decision making (10 occurrences, 43 links), hrm (10 occurrences, 35 links), personnel training (6 occurrences, 30 links), machine learning (8 occurrences, 24 links), artificial intelligence technologies (6 occurrences, 23 links).

The total link strength shows how many times two keywords appear together in an article (Guo, Huang, Guo, Li, Guo, & Nkeli, 2019). In the VOS viewer map indicate thicker the line between two nodes, stronger the connection between them. Therefore, the node "Artificial Intelligence" has thicker lines with "Human Resource Management", resource allocation, natural resources management, human resources management. These nodes are found to have strong link with Supply Chain Management. The relationships of "Artificial Intelligence with "Human Resource Management" seems the close for better production. Subsequently, Ai has also close relation with "resources allocation" it explores that AI can be the best tools as resources allocator.

Bibliographic coupling with temporal analysis

Figure 7. Bibliographic coupling with temporal analysis
 Source: Created through VOS viewers

Figure 7 was run through a chronological analysis between 2015 and 2023. The colour differences determine the date of Bibliographic coupling with Author (figure), it reveals the years of publication (Fachada, Rebelo, Lourenço, Dimas, & Martins, 2022). Among 76 authors only 47 meet the threshold under one minimum author document and 1 author citation. Older themes are represented by the blue which represent (Kshetri, 2020) (Rezzani, Caputo, & Cortese, 2020) (Ochmann & Laumer, 2020) (Tewari & Pant, 2020) (Jia Q., Guo, Li, Li, & Chen, 2020). While newer ones by the yellow which represent (Agarwal, 2023) (Basu, Majumdar, Mukherjee, Munjal, & Palaksha, 2023) (Einola & Khoreva, 2023) (Chowdhury, et al., 2023) (Rodgers, Murray, Stefanidis, Degbey, & Tarba, 2023) (Langer & König, 2023) Result indicate that majority of authors during 2020 wrote conference and in 2023 majority authors diverted to wrote article.

Keyword co-occurrence network with temporal analysis

Keyword co-occurrence analysis was used to detect developing tendencies in AI-HRM. Overlay visualisation looked at the average year of publication for articles containing a given keyword (Guo, Huang, Guo, Li, Guo, & Nkeli, 2019). Overlay visualisation is useful for examining the co-occurrence of keywords, which sheds light on emerging themes (Narong & Hallinger, 2023). Older themes are represented by the blue, which consists of words like artificial intelligence, techno, personnel training, and big data, while newer ones are represented by the yellow, which consists of words like resource management, article, and human. The results indicate that the majority of keywords like article intelligence, human resource management, natural resources management, resource allocation, hrm, competition, and decision making were published between the middle of 2021 and the middle of 2022.

Figure 8: Keyword co-occurrence network with temporal analysis
Source: Created through VOS viewers

Discussion

Data collected from the Scopus database, this article sheds light on the bibliometric analysis of the AIHRM term from 2015 to 2023. In order to identify patterns and hot topics in AIHRM research, this article presents an overview of previous works on the topic.

The authorship that received the most citations (121) belonged to (Vrontis, Christofi, Pereira, Tarba, Makrides, & Trichina, 2022), and the publication that received the most citations (196 with 3 documents) belonged to the International Journal of Human Resource Management. Even though developing nations are also adding to the body of knowledge, most of the study was done in industrialized nations in Europe and Asia. The United Kingdom has the most citations and overall links, making it the strongest nation.

The results of the keyword co-occurrence network analysis (see Figure 5) and the bibliographic reference coupling analysis show that there are seven groups. They are: red clusters which focused on the core concept of AIHRM; the green cluster focused on the ethical issue and stakeholder view towards AIHRM; the Blue cluster focused on interaction between AI and humans; the yellow cluster described the literature review; the purple cluster explained the AI in the candidate recruitment process; the light blue cluster mainly raised the question when do machines and People Merge?; and the orange cluster explored the application of AIHRM.

Keyword co-occurrence networks show that Artificial Intelligence, Human Resource Management, Natural resources management, human resources management, decision

making, HRM, personnel training, machine learning, and artificial intelligence technologies were keywords used in the AIHRM study. A chronological study between 2015 and 2023 that combined bibliographical coupling with temporal analysis shows that the majority of writers published conference papers in 2020 and articles in 2023, which seems to be an increasing trend. Keyword co-occurrence networks with temporal analysis display that the majority of keywords looked published in between the middle of 2021 and the middle of 2022.

Conclusion

The field of AIHRM has recently garnered significant attention and has become a subject of growing interest. There has been a significant increase in the number of publications. Despite this, the publications linked to the core department of HRM appear to be inadequate, and researchers propose adding additional studies on AIHRM from the HRM subject's perspective. Future researchers may consider conducting the study by integrating data from various sources, such as the Web of Science (WOS), Dimensions, PubMed, and Google Scholar, in order to obtain a more comprehensive set of results. Encourage interdisciplinary research partnerships between AI researchers and HRM scholars to narrow the gap between technical AI advances and HRM practices. Promote longitudinal studies to track the evolving trends and impacts of AIHRM over time, facilitating informed decision-making and strategic planning in organizations.

Limitations

Scopus was the only source considered; it is possible that some relevant information was missed. "Human Resource Management" was selected as the focus area. Articles from other fields are thus excluded from the data. The study encompasses a dataset spanning a period of six years only. Insufficient data may result in an inadequate conclusion. The research utilized only a limited set of keywords to search study content, including "Artificial Intelligence," "Human Resource Management," "AI Human Resource Management," "Human Resources Artificial Intelligence," "AI for HRM," and "HRMAI," which scarcity the documents for the study. This study had limitations in terms of data collection, as it did not involve searching through databases like APA PsycInfo, Web of Science or PubMed. As a result, the scope and breadth of the obtained results were restricted.

Appendix

Table A1: Distribution of Authors

Red Cluster		Green Cluster	
SN	Authors	SN	Authors
1	Basu et al., 2023	1	bankins, 2021
2	chowdhury et al., 2023	2	bankins et al., 2022
3	del et al., 2023	3	johnson et al., 2022
4	Einola & khoreva, 2023	4	langer & könig, 2023
5	khalifa et al., 2022	5	park et al., 2022
6	malik et al., 2021	6	prikshat et al., 2023
7	malik et al., 2023		
8	rodgers et al., 2023		
Blue Cluster		Yellow cluster	
SN	Authors	SN	Authors
1	arora et al., 2021	1	jia et al., 2021
2	arслан et al., 2020	2	Kaushal., 2023
3	Figueroa et al., 2020	3	Majumder & mondal., 2020
4	Hmoud, 2021	4	rajpurohit et al., 2020
5	Kshetri, 2020	5	tewari & pant, 2020
6	rauf et al., 2021	6	votto et al., 2021
Purple Cluster		Light Blue cluster	
SN	Authors	SN	Authors
1	Agarwal, 2023	1	abbas et al.,2022
2	ochmann & laumer, 2020	2	johnson et al., 2020
3	rezzani et al.,2020	3	panicker et al., 2020
4	vrontis et al., 2022	4	qamar et al., 2021
5	pan et al 2022		
Orange Cluster			
SN	Authors		
1	bhardwaj et al., 2020		
2	pereira et al., 2023		
3	tiwari et al., 2021		
4	wang & lin, 2020		

Source: Scopus Database, 2015-2023

Table A2: Distribution of keywords

Red Cluster		Green Cluster	
Keyword	Frequency	Keyword	Frequency
Article	5	artificial intelligence technologies	6
artificial intelligence	69	decision making	10
big data	5	human resource management	46
Human	5	human resources management	23
machine learning	8	natural resources management	20
resource management	5	resource allocation	21
Blue Cluster		Yellow Cluster	
Keyword	Frequency	Keyword	Frequency
Competition	5	systematic review	5
Hrm	10		
personnel training	6		

Source: Scopus Database, 2015-2023

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